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THE IMPACT OF ANTHROPOGENIC FACTORS ON FOREST AND SOIL COVER IN MOUNTAINOUS SHIRVAN

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Annotation. *This article examines the current state of forest cover and anthropogenic changes in the river basins of the southeastern part of the Greater Caucasus. The study reveals that the eastern boundary of the forest in the research area has been disrupted due to anthropogenic factors, leading to the degradation of existing forests. This transformation has resulted in forest thinning and replacement by low-productivity tree stands and shrub communities. The degradation of forests contributes to the deterioration of the physical and chemical properties of the soil cover, reducing both its productivity and protective functions. The article is based on materials collected by the author during field research.*

Keywords: *tree stands, soil, forested area, shrubland, anthropogenic factors*

THE IMPACT OF ANTHROPOGENIC FACTORS ON FOREST AND SOIL COVER IN MOUNTAINOUS SHIRVAN

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Summary. *The article is devoted to the current state and the anthropogenic change of forest vegetation in the eastern part of the Great Caucasus. It was revealed that in the object of study the eastern boundary of the forest under the influence of anthropogenic facts was narrowed. The forest vegetation undergoing transformation is replaced by low productive vegetation and various shrub groupings. Degradation of forests leads to deterioration of physical and chemical indicators of soil cover, reduction of its productivity and protective functions. The article is based on field research.*

Key words: *wooden, soil, forest, shrubbery, anthropogenic.*

Introduction

The study of soil and forest cover on the southeastern slope of the Greater Caucasus has been significantly influenced by the research contributions [1,2]. Historically, this region has seen extensive agricultural development, including farming and livestock breeding, followed by horticulture, viticulture, and vegetable cultivation [3]. However, a significant portion of these lands has been subjected to various degrees of erosion and degradation. The composition and boundaries of the forest cover in the study area have undergone considerable changes due to both natural and anthropogenic factors [4]. On the southeastern slope of the Greater Caucasus, relatively undisturbed forest cover has been preserved in the inaccessible areas of the middle mountain forest belt [5]. However, the lower and upper mountain-forest belts have been significantly affected by human activities, leading to alterations in their area and boundaries. In some locations near settlements, the lower and upper forest boundaries have completely disappeared. The forest composition in these areas is predominantly characterized by stands of Persian ironwood (*Parrotia persica*) and hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus*). Due to the high slope gradients in the research areas, soil erosion poses a serious threat to agriculture, highlighting the need for in-depth research in these regions.

Research Object and Methodology. The study was conducted in the southeastern slope of the Greater Caucasus, specifically in the Mustafalichay basin, which is a right tributary of the Aghsuchay River, as well as in the Pirsatchay and Girdmanchay basins. Research was carried out on various slopes using large-scale (1:25,000) forest maps and employing landscape, geobotanical, and biogeographical route survey methods.

Analysis and Discussion. High-density forest cover remains relatively widespread in the left tributaries of the Girdmanchay River and in the Pirsatchay and Aghsuchay basins at elevations of 1,300–1,500 meters above sea level. These forests primarily consist of *Quercus iberica* and *Carpinus caucasica*, covering the southern slopes and experiencing varying degrees of anthropogenic impact. On the northern slopes, *Fagus orientalis* integrates into the hornbeam forests. The forest composition also includes a small proportion of *Acer* sp. and *Taxus baccata* L. In the watershed areas of the slopes, individual and clustered occurrences of *Betula pendula* Roth. and *Sorbus caucasica* Lins. can be observed. In the lower reaches of the Pirsatchay River, the slopes are heavily fragmented by ravines and gullies. Against the backdrop of exposed clay formations, distinctive sparse woodlands have developed, where the dominant species is the many-fruited *Juniperus polycarpus* C. Koch. In the middle mountain-forest belt of the Aghsuchay basin, forest cover has been significantly degraded due to human economic activities. On the southern slopes of this belt, mixed oak-hornbeam forests have emerged from coppice regeneration. Forests with relatively lower levels of anthropogenic disturbance, consisting primarily of eastern beech and hornbeam, are found in the northern tributaries of the Mustafalichay basin, particularly within the Pirgulu State Nature Reserve (Figure 1).

Source: by autor 2023 June. (N 40° 47' 56" E 48° 32' 35")

Figure 1. Oriental beech-hornbeam forest on the right bank of the Mustafalichay (a Tributary of the Aghsuchay).

The research indicated that, on the slope of Girdmanchay facing Baskal village (to the north), at elevations between 1200-1400 meters above sea level, a regeneration-type hornbeam forest has spread. The composition includes small amounts of oak, maple, and ash. The observed features suggest that the existing forest stands have originated from the place of pistachio forests, although pistachio trees are no longer present in the current forest. The replacement of pistachio trees with hornbeam is due to the systematic and repeated cutting of the forest. The presence and dominance of pistachio trees on the analogous slopes of the adjacent mountain confirms this. In the lower and upper mountain-forest zones of the Girdmanchay basin, the forest ecosystems have undergone transformation, resulting in alterations or destruction. In the middle mountainous areas, forests dominated by Iberian oak have been replaced by hornbeam forests of regeneration origin, ironwood stands, and xerophytic shrub communities (such as hawthorn, sumac, buckthorn, juniper, etc.) (Figure 2).

Source: 2023 June. (N 40° 46' 59" E 48° 22' 53")

Figure 2. Young secondary Hornbeam forests (20–30 Years Old) in the Niyaldagh

In the middle mountain-forest zone of the basin, forest ecosystems that have preserved their original state are now very scarce. The pistachio forests have been replaced by regeneration-origin hornbeam forests of young age, and in most cases, various types of shrubbery. On the northern slopes of Niyaldagh, even one hectare of middle-aged or mature tree stands is not found. Here, at an elevation of 1350 meters above sea level, on a steep northern slope, a cleared area used as pasture has given way to dense, regeneration-origin hornbeam stands in place of a pistachio-hornbeam forest. Moving upwards along the mountain slope towards the summit, pistachio trees become more frequent in the composition of young trees. As one ascends Girdimanchay, starting from Lahij, the right bank slopes have almost entirely been deforested. In the southeast slopes of the Greater Caucasus, a continuous forest cover is found throughout the Ağsuçay basin, specifically in the Pirqulu State Nature Reserve. However, much of the forested area here consists of hornbeam forests that have replaced the once dominant pistachio forests, which were subject to human intervention in the past. Currently, these hornbeam forests are around 80-100 years old. The forest is bidominant, with pistachio and hornbeam trees, and in some areas, the second layer of vegetation is made up of qaracöhrə (wild service tree). In the Pirsaat river and Gozluchay basins, anthropogenic impacts have led to more significant changes in the vegetation cover. In the eastern parts of the Pirsaat river basin, the forest cover remains fragmented into small patches. The research conducted in the Shamakhi forestry management area included two experimental plots located at altitudes of 1430 and 1450 meters above sea level on the right bank of the Mustafalı river. These plots were chosen to study the physical-chemical characteristics of the soil cover in two distinct conditions: one in an untouched forest and the other in an anthropogenically affected forest. The physical-chemical indicators of the soil samples from these plots are provided in the table below. The table shows significant differences in the genetic thickness and physical-chemical characteristics of the soil profiles. For example, the humus content in the upper first soil profile horizon is 11.6%, while in the upper A horizon of the profile under the shrubland, it is only 5.3%. The total nitrogen content in these layers is 0.820% in the first profile and 0.368% in the second profile. Other physical-chemical indicators of the soil profiles are detailed in the table 1.

Table 1. Under slightly degraded forest and deforested areas

Plot area	Genetic layer	Depth, cm	Hydroscopic moisture, %	Humus, %	Total nitrogen, N, %	CaCO ₃	Adsorbed bases, 100 g/ m ² soil			pH
							Ca	Mg	Total	
Shamakhi forestry enterprise Pirqulu Area, right bank of Mustafalı River, 1430 m its density 0,9 N-NE-28 ⁰ 800 meters southeast from the 1 st section	Ao	0-5	Forest floor							
	AU	5-14								
	A/	14-37	6,7	11,6	0,820	0,3	26,0	5,0	31,0	5,80
	B	37-75	6,9	5,5	0,434	0,5	22,0	3,8	25,8	6,18
	C	75-94	5,25	1,9	0,112	1,1	20,0	4,0	24,0	6,80
At an elevation of 1450 m above sea level 800 m from the forest, the post-forest steppe grassland.			5,08	0,7	0,074	2,6	15,0	6,0	21,0	7,10
	AU	0-20								
	a	20-45	5,4	5,3	0,368	8,1	24,0	5,0	29,0	7,60
	B	45-69	6,2	2,1	0,163	4	21,0	7,0	28,0	8,10
C			5,32	0,8	0,077	19,6	19,0	7,0	26,0	8,30

The left bank slopes of Pirsaat river (southern side), at elevations ranging from 1110 to 1500 meters above sea level, have been deforested and are composed of various shrub groupings. Only in one place – on the left bank of Pirsaat river – there is a woodland called 'Gonagkand Forest'. The reason the forest has remained here is because it is located on a very steep slope (30-45 degrees). The Gozluchay basin has the lowest percentage of forest cover, with forests only appearing in patches in the middle mountain-forest zone. However, throughout this forest zone, traces of forest cover are observed as isolated trees or groups of trees and shrubs formed in place of the forest. In the 'Pip Gorge' area (the local name for Pistachio) along the river, we recorded a small area of disturbed pistachio trees. Near the village of Pirbeyli (on the left bank of Gozluchay), at elevations ranging from 1250 to 1500 meters above sea level, there are heavily anthropogenically degraded oak and veldt trees. This area can be considered the eastern boundary of the forest in the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus. To the east of this area, traces of forest cover consist only of regenerating shrub formations.

CONCLUSION

The modern eastern boundary of the forest cover in the Greater Caucasus has changed due to anthropogenic influences, leading to the replacement of forests with less productive plant formations (to the west). In the lower mountain-forest zone, forests dominated by Iberian oak have been replaced by regenerating oak forests, ironwood, and xerophytic shrubs due to thinning. In the middle mountain-forest zone, forests that have maintained their original state are rare. Pistachio forests have transformed into veldt forests and various types of shrub formations. In the upper mountain-forest zone, eastern oak and hornbeam forests have been replaced by steppe and shrub formations due to long-term human agricultural activities.

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